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Globalization and its impact on Growth of Indian Economy

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Introduction

Indian economy was in deep crisis in July 1991, when foreign currency reserves had plummeted to almost billion, inflation had roared to an annual rate of 17 percent; fiscal deficit was very high and had become unsustainable; foreign investors and NRI's had lost confidence in Indian economy. Capital was flying out of the country and we were close to defaulting on loans. Along with these bottlenecks at home, many unforeseeable changes swept the economies of nations in Western and Eastern Europe, South East Asia, Latin America and elsewhere, around the same time. These were the economic compulsions at home and abroad that called for a complete overhauling of our economic policies and programs. The new policy regime radically pushed forward in favour of a more open and market oriented economy.

The concept of economic development refers to the process of improvement in the economic opportunities, and quality of human lives; and reduction in the poverty. Better health facilities, better education, clean environment and better utilization of resources are the important components of Economic Development. Moreover the justified distribution of goods and services is also the part of economic development. A good distribution network that includes the good transportation system results in not only better delivery of goods and services but the improvement of labors mobility (Henderson, 2007). In nut shell we can say globalization can be applied is a movement, a phenomenon and a force. And the scope of the globalization is increasing as the time is passing (EuroStat, 2007). One most common definition of globalization states that Globalization is a process of integrating different world economies. Globalization is integration among the people, government and companies of different countries (Rothenberg, 2003).

Globalization

Globalization refers to the Political, Economical, Social and Technological links in different countries (Hamilton & Webster, 2009). Globalization is a contested concept that refers to shrinkage of time and space (Steger, 2009). "Globalization is the diminution or elimination of state-enforced restrictions on exchanges across borders and the increasingly integrated and complex global system of production and exchange that has emerged as a result (Palmer, 2002)." Globalization has changed the picture of World Economy, by increasing the cross-border trade, exchanges of currency, free flow of Capital, movement of people and flow of information. Globalization has introduced the concept of border-less and integrated world economy. Globalization has given a new thought to the businesses worldwide. A lot of Strategic changes have been occurred in the businesses. Now target market for businesses is not only their home land, but the overall world (Intriligator, 2003).

India's Initial Initiative for Globalization

Major measures initiated as a part of the globalization strategy in the early nineties included the following:

- **Devaluation:** the first step towards globalization was taken with the announcement of the devaluation of Indian currency by 18-19 percent against major currencies in the international foreign exchange market. In fact this measure was taken in order to resolve the BOP crisis.

- **Disinvestment** - In order to make the process of globalization smooth, privatization and liberalization policies are moving along as well. Under the privatization scheme, most of the public sector undertakings have been sold to private sector.
- **Dismantling of the industrial Licensing Regime** - A significantly amended locational policy in tune with the liberalized licensing policy is in place. No industrial approval is required from the government for locations not falling within 25kms of the periphery of cities having a population of more than one million.
- **Allowing foreign Direct Investment (FDI)** - across a wide spectrum of industries and encouraging non-debt flows. The department has put in place a liberal and transparent foreign investment regime where most activities are opened to foreign investment on automatic route without any limit on the extent of foreign ownership. Some of the recent initiatives taken to further liberalize the FDI regime, inter alia, include opening up of sectors such as Insurance, development of integrated townships, defence industry, tea plantation, enhancement of FDI limits in private sector banking, allowing FDI up to 100 percent under the automatic route for most manufacturing activities in SEZs; opening up B2B e-commerce; Internet service providers (ISPs) without gateways; electronic mail and voice mail etc. The department has also strengthened investment facilitation measures through foreign investment implementation Authority (FIIA).
- **Non Resident Indian Scheme** - the general policy and facilities for foreign direct investment as available to foreign investors / Companies are fully applicable to NRIs as well. In addition, Government has extended some concessions especially for NRIs and overseas corporate bodies having more than 60 percent stake by NRIs.
- **Throwing open industries reserved for the public sector to private participation**
- **Abolition of the (MRTP) Act**, which necessitated prior approval for capacity expansion.
- **The removal of quantitative restrictions on imports.**
- **Wide-ranging financial sector reforms** - in the banking, capital markets, and insurance sectors, including the deregulation of interest rates, strong regulation and supervisory systems, and the introduction of foreign/private sector competition

Manufacturing Sector in India and Economic Growth

The average GDP growth in the manufacturing sector was 9.52 per cent in the early nineties when the economic reform process was initiated. Thereafter, from 1996-97 onwards a decline in manufacturing sector GDP was witnessed till 2001-02. From 2002-03 there was a revival and the sector recorded an average double digit growth of 10.13 per cent during the period from 2005-06 to 2009-10. But from 2010-11 onwards again a decline in GDP growth was witnessed with the sector recording a negative growth of 0.74 per cent in 2013-14. To give a boost to the manufacturing sector growth and to make the sector globally competitive, the government had announced the National Manufacturing Policy in 2011.

The policy envisaged enhancing the share of manufacturing to GDP from 16 to 25 per cent and to create 100 million jobs by 2022. The policy envisages the Centre to provide an enabling framework and incentives for infrastructure development on a PPP mode and the State Governments to be encouraged to adopt the instrumentalities provided in the policy viz; setting up of National Investment and Manufacturing Zones, Rationalization and simplification of business regulations, Incentives for small & medium enterprises, Industrial training and skill up gradation measures among others. However, the manufacturing sector growth continued to be a cause of concern. Prime Minister in his Independence Day Speech in 2014 invited the world to 'Make in India', 'Manufacture in India' and indicated that growth of manufacturing sector is must for employment generation of the youth. The Make in India initiative announced officially in September 2014, aims to facilitate investment,

foster innovation, enhance skill development, protect intellectual property and build best in class manufacturing infrastructure and convert India into a manufacturing hub of the world.

The manufacturing sector in India is heterogeneous with a preponderance of small unregistered manufacturing units accounting for almost 80 per cent of the employment in the sector with GDP contribution of just 4.5 per cent in 2012-13. In other words the growth of the manufacturing sector is led by registered manufacturing. The average GDP growth in manufacturing sector during the period from 2000-01 to 2012-13 was 7.5 per cent of which registered sector recorded an average growth of 8.7 per cent and unregistered sector an average growth of 5.2 per cent. Despite the industrial policy reforms initiated since 1991 some of the major hurdles in manufacturing sector growth remained viz. poor infrastructure, bureaucratic delays, high cost of capital, delays in land acquisition, labour laws etc . The earlier attempt to set up Special Economic Zones to speed up manufacturing growth met with limited success due to these hurdles.

Make in India Initiative and Prospects for Economic Growth

In the Global Competitiveness Index 2014-15 India is in the 71st position out of a total of 144 countries. In the Global Innovation Index 2015 India ranks 81 out of a total number of 141 countries. As per the World Bank's Ease of Doing Business Ranking 2015 India is ranked 142 among 189 countries. The ranking of the sub-indicators of the Ease of Doing Business Index viz; Starting a business (158th rank), Dealing with construction permits (184th rank), Getting electricity (137th rank), Registering property (121st rank), Getting credit (36th rank), Paying taxes (156th rank), Trading across borders (126th rank), Enforcing contracts (186th rank) and Resolving insolvency (137th rank) only validates the earlier mentioned hurdles as still existing and stifling manufacturing growth. During 2014-15 a slew of measures have been initiated to simplify these hurdles and to bring about ease of doing business in India. The "Make in India" initiatives focuses on 25 key sectors and is based on four pillars, which have been identified to give boost to entrepreneurship in India, not only in manufacturing but also other sectors. The four pillars are:

- **New Processes:** 'Make in India' recognizes 'ease of doing business' as the single most important factor to promote entrepreneurship. A number of initiatives have already been undertaken to ease business environment.
- **New Infrastructure:** Government intends to develop industrial corridors and smart cities, create world class infrastructure with state-of-the-art technology and high-speed communication. Innovation and research activities are supported through a fast paced registration system and improved infrastructure for IPR registration. The requirement of skills for industry are to be identified and accordingly development of workforce to be taken up.
- **New Sectors:** FDI has been opened up in Defence Production, Insurance, Medical Devices, Construction and Railway infrastructure in a big way.
- **New Mind set:** In order to partner with industry in economic development of the country Government shall act as a facilitator and not a regulator. The Government has started the e-biz portal which is a one-stop arrangement for entrepreneurs for online registration, filing returns, seeking license etc. The portal synchronizes the functions of six Government departments viz; the DIPP, DGFT, CBDT, RBI, ESIC, EPFO, Ministry of Corporate Affairs and Petroleum & Explosives Safety Organization at the pan-India level. Labour reforms have been initiated such as in the Apprentices Act, 1961 the provisions have been simplified to enable even the MSME sector to take apprentices, extending apprentice training to non-technical courses, allowing apprenticeship training in informal trades etc. The Labour Laws (Exemption from Furnishing Returns & Maintaining Registers by Certain Establishments) Amendment Act, 2014 extends the provisions of the Act to units holding up to 40 workers

instead of 19 workers and the number of labour laws exempted has been increased from the present 9 to 16. In addition the following labour laws viz; the Industrial Disputes Act, 1947, The Minimum Wages Act, 1948, the Contract Labour (Regulation of Employment & Conditions of Service) Act, 1971 may also be taken up for reform. The proposed Reforms in the Employees' Provident Fund & Miscellaneous Provisions Act, 1952 would extend social security benefits under EPFO to the unorganized sector as well as to more number of units within the organised sector.

The Government is also trying to bring in amendments in some of the so called grey areas such as the indirect tax regime by bringing the Goods & Service Tax through a Constitution (122nd Amendment) Bill 2014, the Right to Fair Compensation & Transparency in Land Acquisition, Rehabilitation and Resettlement (Second Amendment) Bill 2015 with the ultimate goal of simplifying the ease of doing business in India. The initiatives announced under Make in India have started creating a positive investment climate and there was a 48 per cent growth in FDI equity flows during the period from October 2014-April 2015.

FDI Inflows in Indian Industrial Sector

- The cumulative FDI inflows from April 2000 to January 2015 aggregate US \$ 361,320 Million. The cumulative FDI equity inflows from April 2000 to January 2015 aggregate to US \$ 243,107 million (₹. 11,99,386 crores).
- In the financial year 2014-2015, the FDI equity inflows from April 2014 to January 2015 are US \$ 25,526 million compared to US \$ 18,749 million during the corresponding period in 2013-14.
- In the current calendar year 2015, the FDI equity inflows for January, 2015 are US \$ 4,481 million (₹. 27,880 crores) compared to US \$ 2,189 million (₹. 13,589 crores) during the corresponding period in 2014 representing a increase of 105 percent in dollar terms and an increase of 105 percent in rupee terms.

Conclusion

The implications of globalization for a national economy are many. Globalization has intensified interdependence and competition between economies in the world market. These economic reforms have yielded the few significant benefits; Globalization in India had a favorable impact on the overall growth rate of the economy. The pickup in GDP growth has helped improve India's global position. Consequently India's position in the global economy has improved from the 8th position in 1991 to 4th place in 2001; when GDP is calculated on a purchasing power parity basis. Our economy has undergone a paradigm shift. It has expanded by over a hundred times, going from a GDP of ₹.10,000 crore to ₹.100 lakh crore at current prices, to emerge as one of the world's largest. Agriculture's share in this has seen a dramatic drop, from more than 50 percent to less than 15 percent of GDP. And our central government's Twelfth Five Year Plan size of ₹.43 lakh crore, dwarfs the First Five Year Plan size of ₹.2,400 crore. Priorities, strategies and structures dating back to the time of the birth of the Planning Commission, must thus be revisited. The very nature of our planning processes needs to be overhauled to align with this shift in sheer scale.

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